

Designing an In-house Language Placement Test for Technology Students

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Abstract: *In this research paper, we report on the design and implementation of an in-house English language placement test created specifically for technology majors at an engineering university in Japan. The paper explains how the in-house placement test was developed and administered within the university's course management system (Moodle) and compares the student scores of the in-house test with the scores of the CASEC English language test. The paper also reports on how the in-house placement test items were monitored and modified to make further improvements using the item analysis test tools included in Moodle. The test design was successful in that it was able to place students efficiently and effectively into appropriate English language levels using an inexpensive in-house online solution. The project also helped formalize a procedure for instructors to modify the test items to further improve the reliability and validity of the placement test.*

Keywords: Language testing, Placement test, Moodle

Language Testing

Different types of language tests are available to determine language learners' abilities. Language teachers are often tasked with selecting an appropriate language test based on the institution's testing objectives. For example, a proficiency test would be selected to determine test takers' general language competence, whereas a placement test would be used to place students in a suitable level of a language course at the institution (Brown, 2015). In some cases, proficiency tests may also be used as placement tests. In Japan, standardized proficiency tests such as GTEC, Eiken, TOEIC, and TOEFLiBT are often used as a requirement to enter higher educational institutions (MEXT, 2020). After students enroll at a university, their English courses are typically assigned or selected based on their placement test results. Institutions may also repurpose standardized tests as placement tests to save time and costs rather than creating and evaluating a custom-designed

test. A survey of placement tests used at four-year universities in Japan showed that about half of the institutions surveyed use standardized tests such as TOEFL and TOEIC to place their learners into appropriate levels for English instruction (Shimizu, 2002).

While language test developers continually develop, administer, and analyze standardized testing instruments, language instructors must consider both the advantages and disadvantages of administering a language test. Wistner et al. (2009) analyzed two standardized tests: The Oxford Placement Test (OPT) and the Michigan English placement test (MEPT), to investigate whether these tests can effectively function as an English proficiency test for Japanese learners of English. The statistical analysis of their study shows that both tests are reliable. However, they also pointed out problems in the MET distribution's normality and the subsections' reliability. Thomas (1994) argues that standardized tests such as TOEFL do not provide detailed results of each question item, so researchers may not easily be able to determine how well these standardized tests correlate with tests that educators develop in-house. As Brown (2015) mentions, standardized tests can provide general indicators of language proficiency instead of identifying students' weaknesses and strengths in certain areas, so standardized language tests may be limited in revealing language learners' real abilities.

Testing backwash, the effects of testing on teaching and learning, should also be considered. Test validity and reliability are two factors that can negatively affect testing results. Tests should assess class/course objectives. Some standardized tests evaluate only reading and listening skills, so the scores may not accurately reveal the test takers' productive skills. Since universities offer a variety of English classes that typically focus on different language skills, tests should evaluate both receptive and productive skills so that the results more accurately reflect what educators hope to assess. Research suggests that the lack of reliability can be harmful to the learner (Hughes, 2003). A reliable test should be consistent in scoring so that the test itself does not impact test takers' abilities. Some standardized tests provide rubrics explaining details about how the score is calculated and what specific language skills are being measured. However, educators should regularly examine the details of their students' test results and continue to question why some students may score higher or lower on different language assessments.

Placement Testing

Placement tests are used in determining appropriate levels of instruction for learners based on their current competency. Language learning curriculums are typically designed to offer different levels of instruction to advanced, intermediate and beginner-level language learners. Placement tests can provide support for learners' success in language programs, offering instructors and students a reliable and standardized language evaluation which can be used as a starting block to advance. Test results can also provide teachers with valuable indicators such as class expectations, teaching pace, and level-appropriate content.

However, educators must also consider any adverse effects of placement testing. Dividing learners by levels can accentuate psychological, social, or economic issues. A placement test may unintentionally group learners in ways that discriminate against students with different social-economic backgrounds (Bachman et al., 1996). Students placed in lower levels may also feel demotivated and develop feelings of failure. Some literature has suggested that in mixed-level classes,

students with initial lower proficiency levels can excel when met with greater challenges and when working with learners who are performing at higher levels (Hana, 2019).

In-house Test Design

Compared to standardized tests, creating in-house tests can have many benefits. To begin with, teachers can obtain test results immediately. Lloyd and Bufton (2011) developed an original placement instrument that was found to be reliable and valid, and could be used in a situation where there was limited time to place students at proper levels before the start of the semester. The standardized tests that universities use as placement tests, such as TOEFL, TOEIC, and Eiken, often require several days to obtain the test scores. Course instructors must rush to place students into classes before the semester begins. Secondly, institutions with large student populations are tasked with finding affordable testing solutions. Ready-made proficiency tests can be cost-prohibitive. In addition, the content of in-house tests can be continually adapted and updated to match the levels and goals of the institution. Therefore, in-house placement tests can have significant advantages over off-the-shelf standardized tests, and may be better indicators of students' weaknesses and strengths within a specific environment. Identifying students' strengths and weaknesses at the beginning of the semester is crucial for language teachers to better support learner needs.

Generally, Japanese students in engineering majors tend to have lower language proficiency levels compared to English-major students (IIBC, 2022). Standardized tests such as TOEFLiBT and TOEIC can be too challenging, and administering an overly-difficult language test can discourage learners from studying English from the onset of their university experience. If test developers accumulate test result data and regularly adjust the test to appropriately match learner levels, the test results can be more beneficial to both teachers and students. Another point is that test content developed in-house can easily be edited and improved, as essential questions can be added, or invalid questions eliminated. As with many technology-related institutions such as ours, non-English-major students must learn English to conduct research and experiments, and to present at conferences. English tests developed in-house can be tweaked for such English for specific purposes (ESP) situations, and can be used to design language curriculums that better match the needs of learners.

Reliability and Validity of Language Tests

There are obvious merits to developing an in-house placement test, but several issues need to first be considered. In-house tests must be carefully designed and tested to ensure their validity and reliability, and achieving a high level of both can be a time-consuming process for test developers. Al-Adawi and Al-Balushi (2016) argue that invalid and unreliable tests could misplace students in the wrong levels, which can negatively affect their learning attitudes. Messick's (1989) validity framework is a useful benchmark to incorporate when designing a test. Both the reliability and validity of the language test should be assessed over time. To check for test reliability, a recognized test is often employed as a standardized scale. In this study, the CASEC test, outlined in the next section, was used as a reference scale when designing our in-house placement test. A reliable test should give similar or consistent results when repeated. To check that the test is valid, or that it is testing what it is intended to test, we need to assess the test results in view of

test goals. If the purpose of the test is to place learners into different course levels, then it would be necessary that the scores are diverse enough to spread the learners; for example, from basic to intermediate to advanced levels. In addition, each item of the test can be further evaluated to determine its discrimination index. The item's discrimination index provides insight on how well the item separates the higher from the lower performing learners. Therefore, when assessing the validity of a placement test, the test's success of separating learners is more important than the quality of the test. Therefore, developing a reliable and valid in-house test can add an extra burden for test developers, who may already be busy with teaching duties.

CASEC Test

Because of the difficulties and time requirements involved in developing in-house tests, and with checking for reliability and validity factors, institutions often opt to use proprietary language tests. One such language test is CASEC, an Internet-based English test administered by the Japan Institute for Educational Measurement (JIEM). The CASEC test has been in use at our institution for the past five years as both a placement test and as a proficiency test, and is used in this study as the benchmark for the design of our in-house language test.

The CASEC test uses Computer Adaptive Test (CAT) techniques based on Item Response Theory (IRT). This CAT minimizes the test taking time because it can select a question at an appropriate level from a question bank according to the previous answer given by the test taker. Thus, the test results can be more accurate compared to a test system that provides questions randomly (JIEM, n.d.-b). The testing time for CASEC is typically 30 to 40 minutes, compared to 120 minutes for TOEIC. CASEC consists of four sections: 1. Knowledge of Vocabulary 2. Knowledge of Phrasal Expression 3. Listening ability – understanding of main idea 4. Listening ability – understanding of specific information. After the test, scores are displayed with estimated scores of standardized tests such as EIKEN, TOEIC and TOEFL. The TOEIC reference score is derived by computing the past TOEIC scores (self-reported) taken from questionnaires voluntarily answered by CASEC test-takers. According to the CASEC website, there is a positive statistical correlation between CASEC and TOEIC as well as TOEFL scores (JIEM, n.d.-a).

Language Test Design Using Moodle

At our university, approximately 550 freshmen take CASEC as a placement test after entering the university. Because of cost issues and the test's limitations in identifying students' weaknesses and strengths in English skills, there is a greater need to develop an in-house placement test as an alternative. Among various learning management systems (LMS), Moodle was selected to develop our in-house placement test because of several benefits. Moodle is a free, open-source learning management system (LMS), with more than 336 million users in 242 nations in 2022 (Moodle, n.d.). These numbers are increasing daily, showing that Moodle now plays a substantial role in educational settings. Moodle can be accessed from mobile devices, tablets, or traditional personal computers, allowing students to access course content anywhere. Moodle is user-friendly and can minimize learning and training time for test developers to familiarize themselves with its functions. Bulk insert and automatic marking functions are available, so this can save instructors time in creating and assessing a placement test. Moreover, Moodle's flexibility enables test

developers to choose a question type and adjust the weighting of each question. Also, Moodle includes a function to display a detailed statistical analysis of items within a Moodle Quiz, which instructors can use to analyze and identify students' weaknesses and strengths in English. Finally, Moodle LMS includes tools that language teachers can use to design practice and quiz tasks to assess productive skills, such as speaking and writing. This is useful when designing language tasks for curriculums that focus on receptive and productive skills, as it is important that learners be placed in appropriate class levels in order to maximize these skills. While standardized tests such as TOEFLiBT and Eiken evaluate all four skills, the high costs, extended assessment times, and limited feedback associated with these tests are crucial issues.

Placement Testing at our Institution

At our university, as with many Japanese universities, a reliable and economical placement test that can be efficiently conducted online or in a CALL Lab is crucial. The turn-around time is an important consideration as a large number of incoming students (approx. 600) need to be promptly grouped into three levels of English proficiency. Over the years, several different placement test solutions were investigated at our institution, including the TOEIC test, the CASEC test, an in-house paper placement test, and most recently, an in-house online placement test. This study focuses on the implementation of our in-house online placement test which is administered using the Moodle course management system. To better evaluate this placement test, the following research questions were investigated.

Research Questions

- 1 How effective and how efficient is an in-house online placement test at placing students into separate levels of English proficiency? Is it a reliable indicator of students' English language knowledge?
- 2 How closely do scores from the in-house online placement test correlate with a standardized placement test such as CASEC?
- 3 To what extent can the results of the in-house online placement test be used to reinforce or reform the existing language learning curriculum?
- 4 How well does the placement test predict student success in the English courses in which students were placed.

Methodology

Procedure and participants

266 first-year engineering students completed both an in-house Moodle test and the CASEC test online in the beginning of their first semester at university. Students were able to complete both the in-house Moodle test and the proprietary CASEC test in approximately the same amount of time, which ranged between 40 and 60 minutes. After students completed both tests online, the results of the CASEC test were compared to the results of the in-house Moodle test to determine if any positive or negative correlations emerged between the two sets of scores. Since the CASEC test

has been in use at the university for the past five years and used as a placement test, the CASEC test scores have been employed as a standardized scale for this study.

CASEC test

All first-year students were asked to take the CASEC test online before the start of classes in the first semester. The results of the CASEC test were used to place students into a first-year English course. Students are not required to take English but most do to satisfy their required humanities credits. During their first year, most students enroll in two English courses – *Reading/Listening* and *English Projects*. Based on the CASEC scores, students are placed into three levels, simply named: A, B and C levels. The materials and tests for the three levels are identical but the pace and teacher support is adjusted to better match the levels of the students. Students are requested to take the CASEC test again at the end of their first year of university, not as an achievement type test because the CASEC test content is not explicitly taught to the students, but rather as a secondary indicator of their English proficiency levels. Course level adjustments can be considered as students enroll in English courses for their second year of university.

In-house Moodle test

In addition to taking the CASEC test, students also completed an online placement test that was developed in-house within Moodle. Unlike the CASEC adaptive test, all participants attempt 70 items with the in-house Moodle test – 35 grammar and reading items, 30 listening items and five speaking items. Two writing tasks were also required of the participants, where test-takers were asked to write 100 words for two prompts for a total of 200 words, although the results of the writing task were not used for placement purposes, and the writing task scores were not included when comparing the in-house Moodle placement test scores with the CASEC test scores. The reading, grammar, listening and speaking sections are computer-scored, whereas the writing section was human-scored. The maximum score for the placement test is 10, which is equal to 100%.

Results

Descriptive statistics: In-house placement test

For the in-house Moodle test scores shown in Figure 1, the average grade, as well as the median grade, for all 266 test-takers was approximately 60% and the standard deviation was 11%. The score distribution skewness of the in-house Moodle test was -0.34 , and the score distribution kurtosis was 0.92 . The negative skew value shows that the tail on the left side of the score distribution is longer than the right side, meaning that slightly more scores fell to the right of the mean. The Shapiro-Wilk tests did not show a significant departure from the normality, $W(258) = .995$, $p = .571$. Therefore, we can assume that the scores from the in-house Moodle placement test are normally distributed, a requirement for the correlation tests.

Figure 1. Histogram of CASEC Scores

Descriptive statistics: CASEC test

For the CASEC test, the average score was 480 out of 1,000 and the median score was 484. The standard deviation was 86.6, the score distribution skewness was -0.77, and the score distribution kurtosis was 1.96. The Shapiro-Wilk tests did not show a significant departure from the normality, $W(247) = .991, p = .156$, so again we can assume that the scores are normally distributed. A visual check of the distribution in Figure 2 confirms a bell-curve shape for the CASEC test score data.

Figure 2. Histogram of In-house Placement Test Scores

In-house placement test & CASEC test score comparison

Since both the datasets of the in-house placement test scores and CASEC test scores are assumed to be normally distributed, the two sets of scores can be statistically compared against each other to better understand the extent to which students' scores on the in-house test correlated with their scores on the CASEC test. Since the CASEC test has been shown to be a valid indicator of English proficiency (Hayashi, 2001), it can be assumed that if the in-house placement test scores positively correlate with the CASEC scores, the in-house placement test can be administered with greater confidence as it would be capable of effectively placing language learners into appropriate language proficiency levels.

The primary objective of this research was to validate our in-house placement test against an established standardized language test, in this case the CASEC test. The Pearson correlation coefficient is used to measure the strength of a linear association between the scores of the two tests as shown in Figure 3. A comparison of the student scores from the in-house Moodle placement test and the CASEC test revealed a moderate positive correlation, meaning there is a tendency for high Moodle placement scores to go with high CASEC scores (and vice versa). The R score for the Pearson correlation was 0.7059. The result was significant at $p < .05$ and at $p < .01$. Since the CASEC test includes only reading and listening, the in-house placement test was again compared to CASEC using only the listening and reading scores. Again, a moderate positive correlation emerged, meaning there is a tendency for high Moodle placement (reading and listening) scores to align with high CASEC scores (and vice versa). The R score for the Pearson correlation was 0.5632. The result was significant at $p < .05$ and at $p < .01$.

Figure 3. *Correlation of In-house Placement & CASEC Scores*

Correlation of CASEC scores with writing scores

As mentioned earlier, the placement test also included a writing task that was human-scored, although the writing score data was not included in the in-house placement data in this study. The writing section on the in-house Moodle exam was piloted to first obtain a better understanding of the students' writing levels, and secondly to examine whether any positive correlations can be made between the writing scores and the placement test scores of either the CASEC or the in-house Moodle test. Unfortunately, the results of the Pearson Correlation Coefficient calculation showed weak relationships between the variables. The value of R was 0.03 when comparing writing scores with the in-house Moodle test scores. The nearer the R value is to zero, the weaker the relationship.

Placement test scores and course success

Finally, we compared the results of the placement tests to the final course grades of the students' first semester English classes to determine if the placement test was a valuable indicator of the student success in their undergraduate English language courses. The results revealed a weak, although positive, correlation between placement test scores and course success. The Pearson correlation coefficient R score between the CASEC scores and English course scores was 0.5424 and the R Score between the in-house Moodle placement scores and English course scores was 0.4115. An R-Score of 1.0 represents a perfect positive correlation between the two variables.

In-house placement test item assessment

In addition to comparing the in-house placement test results against the CASEC test results, the in-house test was analyzed to determine which test items may be less reliable indicators of language proficiency level. For each placement test item, the following variables were assessed in order to make further improvements on the test. These variables below are easily accessible to teachers via the Moodle quiz statistics report shown in Figure 4.

- Facility index
- Standard deviation
- Random guess score
- Intended weight
- Effective weight
- Discrimination index
- Discriminative efficiency

Figure 4. Moodle Quiz Statistics

Discussion

An important aspect of test development is to determine how well the test measures what it is designed to measure. First validity (construct) of the scores of the in-house Moodle test were compared against a proprietary standardized test. Since our school has been using CASEC as a placement test for several years, and since CASEC scores have a TOEIC equivalent, the CASEC scores were used as a base for comparison with our in-house Moodle scores. The CASEC test has also been assessed by research institutions within Japan and has been shown to be a reliable placement instrument (Hayashi, 2001).

The most encouraging result was that the results revealed positive correlations between the in-house placement test results and the CASEC test results. As mentioned earlier in this paper, the CASEC test scores were used as a common language proficiency level indicator. Since the scores of the in-house placement test positively correlated with the CASEC test scores, we were confident that the in-house placement test scores adequately represented the learners' language proficiency levels and that the in-house placement test adequately placed learners into three language course levels – low, intermediate, and high. In fact, the in-house placement test has possible advantages over the CASEC test in that it includes a speaking and writing component.

In addition to measuring the correlation of the overall placement test scores of the two tests, each item of the in-house placement test was evaluated to make further improvements to the test.

Items that have a low discriminative efficiency are automatically highlighted in Moodle to easily identify items that need to be revised. For example, if most of the students received a similar score on a particular item, then it is unable to distinguish between a lower-level student and a higher-level student, therefore the item is not useful as a placement item and needs to be revised or replaced. A discrimination efficiency of 50% or greater is typically considered effective for a placement test (Quiz report statistics, 2022).

It also proved useful to evaluate the scores for each section of the test in order to make informed curriculum improvements as well as design effective language tasks for the classroom. The placement test in this study reinforced the established assumption that Japanese language learners are typically weaker in speaking and listening skills, as opposed to reading and grammar skills. The facility index (F) value for the listening section was 0.45 while the average discriminative efficiency for the reading and grammar section was 0.70. A lower facility index average for the listening suggest that the students found the listening items more difficult than the grammar items. A facility index of 0.35 to 0.65 indicates that the question difficulty is at a sufficient level to differentiate student levels. Additionally, the average discriminative efficiency for the listening section was 21% while the average discriminative efficiency for the reading and grammar section was 37%. From this data we can assume that the reading and grammar section did a better job as sorting learners than the listening section.

Implications and Limitations

Although the results revealed a positive correlation between the in-house placement test and standardized CASEC test, several important issues should be considered for future research. First, the in-house test developed within Moodle did not include a CAT function, whereas CASEC did include CAT, meaning that each question can be dynamically presented based on the test takers' abilities and levels. Therefore, developing an in-house placement test using a learning platform with CAT abilities could prove useful. Also, the standard CASEC test measures only receptive skills, while the in-house test includes both receptive skills and a speaking component. Results from standardized tests which include productive skills, such as the TOEIC Speaking and Writing test or Eiken test, could also be compared to the in-house test. Moreover, though our study involved over 250 students, a more significant number of participants is required to establish more reliable results that can be compared with standardized tests. In the future, technical support should also be provided to assist learners when they are taking the test, as a few participants were not able to complete the speaking section due to technical issues.

This study also sought to determine how well the in-house test scores statistically reflect the students' writing abilities as well as the learners' final course success. The correlations were not as strong as expected, so further data will be collected to investigate this pattern and possible causes. Lastly, because of time limits, this study did not include feedback collected from the language learners. This could help reveal deeper insights towards students' attitudes and motivational levels after completing the placement test and the English course that they were placed in based on the placement test results.

Conclusion

The overall aim in this study was to explore the challenges practicing teachers face developing a reliable in-house English language placement test for non-English major students at the university level. A standardized test, CASEC, was used to compare the reliability of a pilot in-house placement test that was administered via the Moodle learning management system. The results of the study revealed a moderate positive correlation between the CASEC and the in-house placement test scores. The researchers felt confident that the in-house test results could be used to accurately place students at an appropriate level for the current English curriculum, despite the weak correlational relationships between the writing scores and the in-house test scores. Finally, this study investigated the statistical correlation between students' final grades in their first-year English classes and their in-house test results. Unfortunately, a weak correlation was found between the in-house placement test and the students' final course grades.

Although further research is required to examine the validity and reliability of the in-house placement test, optimistic findings of the overall study include reduction of test costs, a more efficient placement process, and the ability to customize the test to a specific institutional environment. Based on the limitations stated in this study, further data collection will help to continually guide and improve in-house placement test development in our context.

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